

STUDIES IN CO-SOLVENCY. PART IV. SOLUBILITY OF STEARATES OF LITHIUM, SODIUM AND POTASSIUM IN GLYCOLIC MIXTURES*

BY SHREEPATI RAO AND SANTI R. PALIT

Measurements have been made of the solubility of stearates of lithium, sodium and potassium at 35° in binary solvent mixtures one component of which is propylene or diethylene glycol and the other is chloroform, ethylene dichloride or benzene. A few measurements have been recorded using alcohols in place of glycols in the above binary mixtures.

It is observed that the glycolic mixtures improve to a great extent the solvent power of the individual solvents and the results are found to be in agreement with previous observations and the already postulated mechanism.

It has been already shown in previous papers (Palit, this *Journal*, 1942, 19, 271; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 3120; Palit and McBain, *J. Amer. Oil Chem Soc.*, 1947, 24, 190) of this series that soaps of alkali metals and heavy metals dissolve strongly in mixtures of a glycol (here called G-solvent for brevity) and a hydrocarbon-dissolving solvent (called H-solvent) such as hydrocarbons, chlorinated hydrocarbons, higher alcohols and the like. This co-solvency is attributed to the existence of polar-nonpolar combination in the soap molecule, the polar oxygen in the $-\text{COO}^-$ group being solvated and thus dissolved through hydrogen bonds with the glycols, and the hydrocarbon portion being dissolved by the other co-solvent in the G-H mixture.

So far no work has been published with the stearates of lithium and potassium and the present paper presents the results on these substances. Data on lithium soap are of special interest as they have been lately used to a larger extent in the manufacture of lubricating grease to impart to it special properties. New data for sodium stearates have also been included for comparison and also because the previous work was done with rather impure samples of stearic acids, whereas a very pure sample of stearic acid has been used in this investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Stearic acid was obtained by the following method of purification. Commercial triple pressed stearic acid was converted into its lead soap and the liquid acids were separated from the solid acids by fractional crystallisation in alcohol (Hilditch, "The Chemistry of Fats and Oils," 1947, p. 468). The solid acids were first converted into the ethyl esters which were fractionated in vacuum twice and were hydrolysed to get back the stearic acid. The stearic acid was next converted into the methyl ester and fractionated three times under vacuum and a constant boiling fraction of methyl stearate was isolated; this fraction was saponified to get stearic acid which was observed to have a melting point of 68.5°. It was then dissolved in alcohol and boiled with active animal charcoal and the solution was filtered hot and allowed to crystallise. The crystals of stearic acids were recrystallised twice more from alcohol and were used in the present experiments.

* Contribution No. 11 from the Department of Physical Chemistry, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Calcutta.

TABLE I
Solubility of soaps at 35° in co-solvent mixtures, (g./100 g. solvents)

Composition of solvent.	Volume per cent glycol (volume per cent alcohol where no glycol is present)										Curve No.		
	0.	10	20.	30.	40.	50.	60.	70.	80.	90.		100.	
Propylene glycol-chloroform	0.00	—	0.58	—	0.56	—	0.24	—	0.068	—	0.04	1	
Propylene glycol-ethylene dichloride	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.06	0.09	—	0.18	—	0.19	—	0.04	2	
Propylene glycol- <i>n</i> -butyl alcohol	0.03	0.101	0.15	0.16	0.17	—	0.16	—	0.12	—	0.04	3	
					(b) Sodium stearate.								
Propylene glycol-chloroform	0.00	—	4.25	—	7.55	7.90	6.79	—	3.86	—	1.68	14	
Propylene glycol-ethylene dichloride	0.00	—	1.70	—	3.27	3.98	3.87	—	2.96	—	1.68	15	
Diethylene glycol-ethylene dichloride	0.00	—	1.32	—	2.07	2.28	2.36	—	2.04	—	1.04	16	
Diethylene glycol-chloroform	0.00	—	3.98	—	4.35	3.91	3.34	—	1.80	—	1.04	17	
					(c) Potassium stearate								
Propylene glycol-chloroform	0.01	4.83	9.17	13.70	16.40	—	18.16	—	15.57	—	6.35	4	
Propylene glycol-ethylene dichloride	0.00	3.22	6.97	9.33	11.02	—	14.50	—	13.54	—	6.35	5	
<i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol-benzene	0.00	0.04	0.14	0.26	0.37	—	0.50	—	0.52	—	0.47	6	
<i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol-chloroform	0.01	0.05	0.10	0.23	0.34	—	0.43	—	0.51	—	0.47	7	
Methanol-chloroform	0.01	0.44	1.17	1.87	2.41	—	3.19	—	3.98	—	4.58	8	
Ethyl alcohol-chloroform	0.01	0.23	0.75	1.19	1.46	—	1.66	—	1.55	—	1.42	9	
Propylene glycol-benzene	0.00	8.28	14.14	18.55	21.08	—	25.60	—	20.52	—	6.35	10	
Diethylene glycol-benzene	0.00	9.75	15.83	21.05	23.51	—	24.24	—	18.24	—	6.54	11	
Diethylene glycol-chloroform	0.01	6.92	12.90	17.10	19.92	—	22.04	—	16.34	—	6.54	12	
Diethylene glycol-ethylene dichloride	0.00	—	7.93	—	13.13	14.60	15.40	—	12.86	—	6.54	13	

Stearates of sodium and potassium were obtained by the usual method of neutralising stearic acid in aqueous alcohol with the requisite amount of caustic solution free from carbonate. Lithium stearate was prepared by precipitating warm lithium chloride in slight excess with warm sodium stearate solution and washing the precipitated lithium stearate repeatedly with warm water until free from chloride. The stearates were dried at 110° for 3 hours and stored in vacuum desiccators.

Solubility measurements were done by the method described before (Palit, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, *loc. cit.*). The analysis of the saturated solution was carried out by the direct titration method (Palit, *Oil & Soap*, 1946, 23, 58; *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1946, 18, 246) with standard perchloric acid in ethylene glycol-isopropyl alcohol mixture (1: 1) using thymol blue as an indicator. *N*/32 normal acid was used for measurements with lithium stearate and *N*/10 normal acid was used for measurements with sodium and potassium soaps. Even with such a dilute solution of perchloric acid the end-point could be determined with great accuracy, the colour of the thymol blue changing sharply from yellow to red at the equivalence point.

The results are presented in Table I and graphically represented in Fig. 1, 2 and 3. For convenience of reference all co-solvency curves (seventeen in all) have been drawn as in previous publications with pure *i. e.*, 100% glycolic solvent on the right hand extreme of the diagram. It may be noted that our present results with sodium stearate are fairly consistent with our previous data (Palit, *this Journal*, *loc. cit.*) if allowance is made for a temperature difference of 10°. On comparing curves 1, 4 and 14 against those of stearates of heavy metals (Pb, Ca, Mg and Zn) in the same solvent mixture *e. g.*, propylene glycol-chloroform (Palit and McBain, *loc. cit.*) it is observed that Li, Na and K stearates show maximum co-solvency at a higher proportion of the glycolic solvent which points to the fact that the alkali metal soaps are more polar than the heavy metal soaps.

DISCUSSION

Comparison of Li, Na and K.—It will be observed from Fig. 1 where we have collected the co-solvency curves for Li, Na and K in the same solvent mixtures, propylene glycol-ethylene chloride and also propylene glycol-chloroform, that all the systems show a striking degree of co-solvency, the solubility in the glycol being increased over three times by adding a non-solvent, *e.g.*, chloroform or ethylene dichloride. The solubility in general varies in the order: potassium \gg sodium $>$ lithium. It is remarkable that though the lithium soap is extremely insoluble, it unmistakably shows the phenomenon of co-solvency in glycolic mixtures even at such low solubility.

In Fig. 1 we have also included the curve for the solubility of potassium stearate in propylene glycol-benzene mixture (curve 10) which is found to run at the top of all other curves. The measurement with this immiscible liquid pair has been made possible by the fact that the addition of potassium stearate brings about a complete miscibility. The same is also true of diethylene glycol-benzene system with potassium stearate the curve (No. 11) for which is presented in Fig. 2. That benzene is a better co-solvent than the chlorinated hydrocarbons has also been previously observed (Palit,

J. Amer. Chem. Soc., loc. cit.) in the case of sodium oleate and this is now found to be true for potassium stearate.

Alcohols as Glycolic Solvents.—In order to test how far the glycolic property is possessed by monohydric alcohols, experiments were conducted to determine the solubility of potassium stearate in chloroform-alcohol mixtures. Potassium stearate was chosen for study as it was felt that the solubility of the other two soaps was too small to definitely reveal such co-solvency, if it existed to only a small degree. Of the three alcohols tested (methyl, ethyl and *n*-butyl) it will be observed from Fig. 3 that methyl alcohol (curve No. 8) shows a practically linear curve, whereas there is a slight convexity in the case of ethyl alcohol (No. 9); butyl alcohol (No. 7), however, shows a very small though definite maximum. This shows that alcohols have very poor co-dissolving power for alkali metal stearates and this co-dissolving power seems to increase with higher alcohols. That this weak co-dissolving power of butyl alcohol is real is further shown by the fact that when chloroform is substituted by benzene in the above study there is observed, as would be seen from Fig. 2 (No. 6), a stronger co-

FIG. 1
Co-solvency curves

Lithium stearate in propylene glycol-chloroform (1), -ethylene dichloride (2), -benzene (3), (ordinates of 1, 2 and 3 have been 10 times magnified); sodium stearate in propylene glycol-chloroform (14), -ethylene dichloride (15); potassium stearate in propylene glycol-benzene (10), -chloroform (4) and -ethylene dichloride (5).

solveny in conformity with the already established fact that benzene is a stronger H-cosolvent than chloroform. It will be further observed that the co-solveny maximum for ethyl alcohol occurs much towards the left of the maximum for butyl alcohol con-

FIG. 2
Co-solveny curves

Potassium stearate in diethylene glycol-benzene (11), -chloroform (12) and -ethylene dichloride (13) ; sodium stearate in diethylene glycol-chloroform (17) -ethylene dichloride (16). (The ordinates of curves 16 and 17 have doubly magnified).

FIG. 3
Solubility in mixed solvents

Potassium stearate in CHCl_3 -MeOH (8), chloroform-ethyl alcohol (9), chloroform-*n* butyl alcohol (7) and benzene-*n*-butyl alcohol (6). (The ordinates of curves 6 and 7 have been magnified 15 times for convenience in representation).

sistent with the fact that ethyl alcohol contains less proportion of hydrocarbon than butyl alcohol.

We had previously observed (Palit, *loc. cit.*) that among aliphatic alcohols methyl alcohol was the best solvent for sodium oleate. Here, for potassium stearate, we observe the same behaviour.

Comparison of Chloroform and Ethylene Dichloride.—We have five pairs of curves (1 & 2, 4 & 5, 12 & 13, 14 & 15, 16 & 17) for comparison between chloroform and ethylene dichloride. All the five pairs show the following common features. Firstly, the co-solvency maximum for ethylene dichloride always occurs on the right of the corresponding maximum with chloroform. This agrees with our previous findings with sodium stearate and sodium oleate. In three cases the difference is only of a few per cent, but in the remaining two cases the maxima are widely separated; for example, with lithium stearate the maxima are at 29 and 72 volume per cent propylene glycol for chloroform and ethylene dichloride respectively, and for sodium stearate the corresponding figures are 33 and 60 volume per cent using diethylene glycol as the glycolic co-solvent. It is noteworthy that for sodium stearate, though the maxima are only separated by only 5 volume per cent units with propylene glycol, the separation becomes widened to over 25 units by passing to diethylene glycol.

Secondly, in all the five pairs it is observed that the maximum solubility reached with chloroform under otherwise identical conditions is always higher than that obtainable with ethylene dichloride. This also agrees with our previous observations with sodium oleate and stearate, and may be interpreted as showing that chloroform is a better hydrocarbon-dissolving solvent than ethylene dichloride.

Comparison of the two Glycols.—In this paper we have not presented any data for ethylene glycol as the H-cosolvents used herein *i. e.*, chloroform-ethylene dichloride, etc., are too immiscible with it to be amenable to such co-solvency measurements. From all our previous and also present data with sodium stearate and oleate, we found propylene glycol (P. G.) a much better solvent than diethylene glycol (D. G.) for the pure soap. In potassium stearate we have met the reverse behaviour. Weight per weight, D. G. is found to be a slightly better solvent than P. G. for K-stearate. However, the co-solvency curves for D. G. with both chloroform and ethylene dichloride run higher above the corresponding curves for P. G. in agreement with our previous work. P. G. has also been found to require less H-solvent than D. G. to produce the maximum solubility which is expected from the already established fact that D. G. is a stronger glycolic solvent than P. G. (*vide*, Fig. 6, Palit, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, *loc. cit.*).

Stearates and Oleates compared.—On comparing the present data for sodium stearate with the previously published data on sodium oleate it is observed that as expected the stearates are much less soluble than the oleates. Further, for sodium stearate the co-solvency maximum always occurs more towards the left hand side (*i. e.*, glycol-poor region) than the corresponding point for the sodium oleate. This is easily understandable as stearate being more hydrocarbon-like and less soluble in hydrocarbons requires a higher proportion of H-solvent to bring about the maximum possible solubility.

Height and Position of the Co-solvency Maxima.—The general trends of these two

features of the maxima are in general agreement with what would be expected if we accept the picture that the co-solvency arises from the fact that the hydrocarbon portion is dissolved by the H-cosolvent and the $-COO^-$ portion is dissolved by the G-cosolvent as previously postulated and as shown below.

We are, however, as yet far from deducing any quantitative guide as to an approximate idea of these two features. For example, if we are confronted with the question of giving an approximate idea of the height and position of the co-solvency maximum in an hitherto uninvestigated soap system, say, sodium laurate in diethylene glycol-chloroform mixture, it becomes difficult to make any quantitative prediction. Our already observed findings make us bold to presage that the position of the maximum will be towards the right side of that of sodium stearate or myristate under identical conditions, and also towards the left side of the maxima for the same system using ethylene dichloride in place of chloroform, or propylene glycol in place of diethylene glycol. We can further say that the per cent increase of the maxima over the mean solubility at that composition will be less than that of its higher homologues.

The authors desire to express their thanks to Sri Ranajit Sengupta for carrying out a major part of the work for the purification of the stearic acid used in this investigation.

PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
 INDIAN ASSOCIATION FOR THE CULTIVATION
 OF SCIENCE, CALCUTTA—12

Received July 12, 1949.